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Governance and Sustainable Development Goal One (SDG1) “No Poverty” in Africa

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Abstract: *This study investigates the impact of governance quality on the attainment of Sustainable Development Goal One (SDG1 – No Poverty) across 45 African countries between 2015 and 2021. The analysis addresses a critical gap in existing literature by assessing how three dimensions of governance—political, economic, and institutional—affect distinct SDG1 sub-indicators: poverty incidence (SDG1.1.1), access to basic services (SDG1.4.1), and dependence on official development assistance (SDG1.a.1). A panel dataset was constructed using indicators from the World Governance Indicators and the World Development Indicators. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was applied to synthesize governance metrics, while a two-step System Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) was employed to estimate dynamic relationships, controlling for endogeneity and serial correlation. Findings reveal that improvements in political and economic governance significantly reduce poverty rates and enhance employment above the poverty line. Institutional governance, while less impactful on direct poverty indicators, significantly lowers reliance on foreign aid. Government effectiveness and political stability positively influence access to drinking water, whereas better governance overall corresponds to reduced levels of official development assistance for poverty alleviation. Control variables such as GDP per capita and infant mortality rates exhibit strong associations with poverty outcomes, reinforcing the multidimensional nature of SDG1 determinants. The study underscores the centrality of governance reform in advancing poverty eradication in Africa. It provides empirical evidence to guide policymakers in designing governance-centered poverty reduction strategies, while highlighting the potential of robust institutions and accountable governance to reduce aid dependency and foster sustainable, inclusive development.*

Keywords: *Governance quality; Sustainable Development Goals (SDG1); Poverty reduction; System GMM estimation*

1. Introduction

The Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) represented the initial global effort to address extreme poverty and basic healthcare needs. Comprising eight well-defined and measurable goals, the MDGs sought to tackle poverty, education, gender equality, child mortality, maternal health, disease, environmental sustainability, and global partnerships for development (Bağ, 2024). While the MDGs achieved notable progress, their outcomes were uneven, necessitating a more comprehensive framework. Consequently, the United Nations (UN) adopted the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in 2015 as an all-encompassing, universally applicable, and human rights-centered agenda. Building upon the foundation laid by the MDGs, the SDGs introduced additional objectives aimed at ensuring sustainable and inclusive growth (Vaidya & Chatterji, 2020). Among these, SDG1 (No Poverty) is particularly significant, as it seeks to eradicate extreme poverty in all its forms by 2030, currently defined as individuals living on less than \$2.15 per day (The Global Goals, 2023).

The urgency of achieving SDG1 is underscored by the disparities observed across different regions. In the Middle East and North Africa (MENA), Tunisia leads in overall SDG performance with a score of 72.50 out of 100, ranking 58th globally, followed by Morocco in 70th place with a score of 70.87. Conversely, Syria and Yemen exhibit some of the lowest SDG completion rates in the region, with scores of 58.18 and 46.85, ranking 130th and 163rd, respectively. In Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA), Cabo Verde and Mauritius have demonstrated the most progress toward overall SDG goals, ranking 89th and 93rd globally with scores of 68.84 and 67.98, respectively. However, Nigeria lags significantly, scoring 54.27 and ranking 146th. The Central African Republic and South Sudan are positioned at the lowest end of the spectrum, ranking 165th and 166th globally, with total scores of 40.40 and 38.68, respectively. These rankings highlight the considerable gap that African nations must bridge to achieve SDG1 and other SDG targets (Sustainable Development Report, 2023).

Despite ongoing efforts, extreme poverty remains a pervasive issue in Africa, exacerbated by inadequate governance structures. Governance has increasingly been recognized as a critical determinant of economic and social outcomes. The World Bank attributed the underwhelming economic performance of many developing countries, particularly in Africa, to deficient governance practices. This issue was first highlighted in 1988 in a World Bank report assessing a decade of experience with structural adjustment loans, which identified significant institutional and managerial deficiencies as key obstacles to economic progress (Kerandi, 2008). Given its integral role within SDG16—focused on "Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions", governance is a fundamental driver of sustainable development. Effective, accountable, and inclusive institutions at all levels are essential for fostering economic growth and social equity. Balasubramanian et al. (2022) further emphasize that enhanced participation and inclusivity in governance positively impact poverty reduction efforts.

Recent trends in governance and poverty in Africa highlight the ongoing challenges faced by the continent. Between 2014 and 2023, governance steadily declined in about 21 African countries affecting close to half of the population. A significant part of this decline is linked to the worsening state of security and rule of law (Reuters, 2024). The Ibrahim Index of African Governance further reports a decline in governance, particularly in the 'Security & Rule of Law' category, which has seen the most significant drop since 2014 (African Law Business, 2024). This decline in governance is compounded by widespread perceptions of corruption, with 91% of countries scoring below 50 on the Corruption Perceptions Index, indicating systemic challenges within key institutions such as the police and judiciary (African Development Bank, 2023). These governance issues are directly linked to the persistent high levels of poverty in the region, as nearly 490 million people in Africa lived in extreme poverty in 2021, with 36% of the population subsisting on less than \$2.15 per day (DevelopmentAid, 2023). Moreover, child malnutrition remains a critical issue, with 34% of children under five facing malnutrition (WorldMetrics, 2023). Limited access to basic services, such as sanitation and electricity, further exacerbates these challenges, with only 27% of Africans having access to sanitation and 29% to electricity (WorldMetrics, 2023). Additionally, youth unemployment rates are alarmingly high, with 57% of African youth either unemployed or underemployed (WorldMetrics, 2023). These statistics underscore the complex relationship between governance and poverty, calling for urgent reforms to improve both governance and economic conditions to foster sustainable development.

This study seeks to bridge the gap in existing literature by examining the relationship between governance and SDG1 (No Poverty) in Africa. While extensive research has been conducted on governance and economic development separately, limited studies have specifically analyzed their interconnection in the context of SDG1. By addressing this gap, the study contributes to a nuanced understanding of how governance indicators influence poverty reduction efforts. The research employs three dimensions of governance; political, economic, and institutional governance (Asongu & Odhiambo, 2020) to assess their impact on SDG1 outcomes. These dimensions were chosen due to their direct correlation with economic policies, institutional frameworks, and social welfare programs essential for poverty eradication.

The study employs a mono-method approach, incorporating quantitative analysis to comprehensively evaluate governance and its effects on poverty alleviation. Quantitative data from global governance and development indices will be used to measure correlations between governance quality and SDG1 achievements across African nations. By integrating governance into the discourse on poverty

reduction, this study offers valuable contributions to both academic literature and policy-making. It provides empirical evidence on the role of governance in achieving SDG1, informing policy decisions aimed at enhancing institutional effectiveness and promoting sustainable economic development in Africa. Ultimately, the findings aim to support the formulation of targeted interventions that strengthen governance mechanisms, thereby accelerating progress toward eradicating extreme poverty across the continent.

2. Literature Review

While there is extensive research on governance and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), limited attention has been given to the relationship between governance and Sustainable Development Goal 1 (SDG 1) in Africa. This gap is critical, as governance structures directly influence the achievement of SDG 1, particularly in regions with entrenched poverty like Sub-Saharan Africa.

Forestier and Kim (2020) analyzed the prioritization of SDGs by national governments, using both quantitative and qualitative methods. The study employed Voluntary National Reviews (VNRs) to ensure a manageable, unbiased, and representative sample, considering income levels and geographical regions. Their analysis of 19 VNRs from 8 lower-middle-income, 5 upper-middle-income, and 6 high-income countries revealed that most countries prioritize specific SDGs, with an average of 4.7 SDGs per country. Notably, Bhutan and Vietnam were analyzed to offer context-specific insights into the factors influencing SDG prioritization. The findings indicated that their SDG prioritization stemmed from pre-existing national policies rather than the introduction of the SDGs, with international organizations influencing their choices.

Barbier and Burgess (2021) examined the relationship between institutional quality, governance, and SDG progress from 2000 to 2018, covering global, low-income, and nine representative developing countries. They found a moderate correlation between SDG welfare gains and institutional quality, with a stronger connection to reduced country risk, underscoring the importance of effective governance for achieving SDG targets. Vyas-Doorgapersad (2021) investigated the effectiveness of global governance reforms in achieving SDG1 (no poverty) in the BRICS countries (Brazil, Russia, India, China, South Africa). The study found that the effectiveness of global governance in these countries depends on addressing legitimacy and representation issues, suggesting that BRICS nations face challenges in fully achieving SDG1 due to governance-related limitations.

Sadiq et al. (2023) analyzed the influence of Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) factors on SDG achievement in ASEAN countries from 1986 to 2020. Their study found a positive relationship between ESG scores, economic growth, and SDG progress, emphasizing that businesses focusing on eco-friendly practices and effective social governance contribute significantly to SDG achievements. Ahmed and Anifowose (2023) assessed the impact of corruption and corporate governance on SDGs in 42 African nations between 2017 and 2020. They found that corruption negatively affects SDGs, while corporate governance has a positive and significant impact, especially in countries with high corruption, highlighting the importance of governance for sustainable development in Africa. Allen et al. (2022) reviewed over 400 academic papers to assess how governance influences poverty and inequality reduction. The study found that investments are accountable, transparent, and inclusive governance have a positive impact on poverty reduction and inequality, supporting the achievement of SDG1.

Leke and Monisola (2015) examined the relationship between governance and poverty reduction in Nigeria. They argued that ineffective governance is a significant barrier to development and poverty reduction. The study therefore recommended a comprehensive anti-poverty strategy that restructures government systems to enhance participation, accountability, and political inclusion. Kwon and Kim (2014) analyzed governance and poverty reduction across 98 countries, finding that good governance is particularly beneficial for poverty reduction in middle-income countries, highlighting the need to address structural inequality in developing regions. Haldar et al. (2023) investigated the role of governance and renewable energy in mitigating energy poverty in 22 Sub-Saharan African countries from 2000 to 2018. They found that government expenditure contributes to economic growth and reduces energy poverty, emphasizing the need for transparent governance, strong institutions, and resilient infrastructure to combat energy poverty.

Ogunniyi et al. (2020) explored the effects of remittances and governance quality on food and nutrition security in Sub-Saharan Africa from 1996 to 2015. Their study found that the interaction between remittance and governance quality positively impacts food security, with control over corruption having the most significant effect. Ayodeji and Abdulganiyu (2022) examined the impact of governance on poverty in Nigeria from 2010 to 2021. Despite challenges like declining oil prices and the COVID-19 pandemic, the study found that governance patterns have significantly influenced Nigeria's economic performance, particularly through inflation and exchange rates, which in turn affects the level of poverty. Akpan and Effiong (2012) explored the link between governance and development performance in 21 Sub-Saharan African countries from 1998 to 2007. They found that the rule of law, regulatory quality, and political stability positively relate to development outcomes, underscoring the importance of institutional reforms in stimulating regional development. Asongu and Odhiambo (2021) analyzed the effect of income-oriented governance on inclusive human development in Sub-Saharan Africa. Their study found that governance had a more pronounced effect on inclusive human development in middle-income countries, and hence, reinforcing the need to strengthen governance for inclusive development. Dankumo et al. (2021) investigated the role of governance, public spending, and trade in poverty reduction in Sub-Saharan Africa from 1996 to 2019. Their findings highlighted that controlling corruption, ensuring political stability, and increasing government spending and trade are associated with poverty reduction, particularly through enhancing the Human Development Index (HDI).

While substantial literature exists on the relationship between governance and poverty reduction, this review has highlighted that research specifically addressing the roles of political, economic, and institutional governance in achieving SDG 1 remains limited, especially in the African context. The reviewed studies highlight the need for further exploration into how these three governance dimensions interact with poverty reduction efforts across African nations.

3. Methodology

The data used for the study covers the period 2015 to 2021. A panel set of 45 African countries were collected from three sub-indicators of governance: political governance (Polgov), economic governance (Ecogov), and institutional governance (Instgov). The reason for selecting these indicators of governance was due to their relevance to the mechanisms that drive poverty reduction. These governance indicators were derived using Principal Component Analysis (PCA) to combine key governance variables: political stability and voice and accountability for Polgov, government effectiveness and regulatory quality for Ecogov, and rule of law and control of corruption for Instgov. Each of these governance sub-indicators was chosen based on its ability to capture critical aspects of governance which directly influences poverty reduction efforts. Political governance, for instance, reflects the stability and inclusiveness of political institutions, which can influence policies aimed at poverty alleviation. Economic governance captures the efficiency and regulatory frameworks that shape economic policies, which are essential for economic growth and equitable distribution of resources. Institutional governance emphasizes the legal and institutional frameworks needed to ensure corruption control, property rights, and effective public administration, which are key drivers of sustainable development.

The use of only three sub-indicators of poverty namely SDG1.1.1 (employed population below the international poverty line by sex and age), SDG1.4.1 (proportion of population using basic drinking water services), and SDG1.a.1 (official development assistance grants for poverty reduction) was because of data availability and unevenness across countries. These indicators hindered the inclusion of additional poverty-related indicators, these three were deemed the most reliable and reflective of the diverse poverty reduction strategies across the sample countries.

This research utilized a quantitative method, drawing on secondary data obtained from the World Bank Development Indicators (WDI) and the Worldwide Governance Indicators (WGI) database covering the years 2015 to 2021. Indicators were meticulously chosen for their empirical and theoretical significance in reducing poverty.

3.1 Model Specification

The model adopted for this study follow empirical model found in the work of Arellano & Bond (1991) has been modified by Asongu & Odhiambo (2021). The functional form of the model is specified as follows:

$$SDG1_{it} = f[Gov_{it}, GG_{it}, X_{it}, SDG1_{it}, \mu_{it}] \tag{1}$$

where:

- SDG1 – Sustainable Development Goal One is operationalized using three proxy indicators: SDG1.1.1 (proportion of the employed population living below the international poverty line, disaggregated by sex and age), SDG1.4.1 (proportion of the population with access to basic drinking water services, by location), and SDG1.a.1 (official development assistance grants allocated for poverty reduction, expressed as a percentage of gross national income by recipient country).
- Gov – refers to Governance proxies by indicators of governance according to World Governance Index (WGI) which are voice and accountability (VA), regulatory quality (RQ), rule of law (RL), control of corruption (CC), government effectiveness (GE) and political stability (PS).
- GG – depicts three different dimensions of governance according to Asongu & Odhiambo (2021). PCA was used to create three new variables namely political governance termed ‘Polgov’, Economic governance termed ‘Ecogov’ and Institutional governance termed ‘Instgov’.
- X – Control variables which includes Inflation, GDP per capita, Population growth, Mortality rate and Gross capital formation.
- $SDG1_{t-1}$ – Lagged value of SDG1.
- i = Country.
- t = Time.
- μ = Error term.

The inclusion of the lag variable changes it to a dynamic model. The econometric form of the model can be expressed as:

$$SDG1_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 Gov_{it} + \beta_2 Polgov_{it} + \beta_3 Ecogov_{it} + \beta_4 Instgov_{it} + \beta_5 CPI_{it} + \beta_7 POPG_{it} + \beta_8 MTR_{it} + \beta_9 GCF_{it} + \beta_{10} SDG1_{it-1} + \mu_{it} \tag{2}$$

3.2 Nature, Sources of Data and Variable Description

The study examined the relationship between governance and SDG1 “No Poverty” in Africa. It utilized a panel dataset comprising 45 countries, including Algeria, Angola, Benin, Botswana, Burundi, Burkina Faso, Cabo Verde, Cameroon, Central African Republic, Chad, Congo Republic, Cote d'Ivoire, Congo Democratic Republic, Egypt, Eswatini, Ethiopia, Gabon, Gambia, Ghana, Guinea, Guinea-Bissau, Kenya, Lesotho, Liberia, Madagascar, Malawi, Mali, Mauritania, Mauritius, Morocco, Mozambique, Namibia, Niger, Nigeria, Rwanda, Senegal, Sierra Leone, South Africa, Sudan, Tanzania, Togo, Tunisia, Uganda, Zambia, and Zimbabwe, across the period of 2015-2021. The study area was chosen to fill existing research gap since much work has been written on the relationship between governance and SDG1 in Sub-Sahara Africa due to data availability and the period of study was also chosen mainly on the basis of data availability. The secondary data sources included the World Governance Indicator, World Development Indicator, and United Nations Sustainable Development Goals.

The brief description of each of the variables along with its relevant source is presented in Table 1.

Table1. Description of variables

Variable notation	Definition	Measurement	Unit of measurement	Source(s)
SDG1	No Poverty	SDG1.1.1, SDG1.4.1 and SDG1.a.1		United Nations Sustainable

				Development Goals(UNSDG).
GOV	Governance	Voice and accountability (VA), Regulatory Quality (RQ), Rule of Law (RL), Control of Corruption (CC), Government Effectives (GE) and Political Stability (PS).		World Governance Indicators, World bank.
Polgov	Political governance	Principal component Analysis (political stability and voice and accountability)		World Governance Indicators, World bank
Ecogov	Economic governance	Principal component Analysis (government effectiveness and regulation quality)		World Governance Indicators, World bank
Instgov	Institutional governance	Principal component Analysis (rule of law and control of corruption)		World Governance Indicators, World Bank
CPI	Consumer price index (2010 = 100)	Measured as an annual percentage change in the cost to the average consumer of acquiring a basket of goods and services.	Index	World Development Indicators, World Bank.
POPG	Population growth (annual %)	Calculated by dividing the difference between the current year's population and the previous year's population by the previous year's population, then multiplying the result by 100 to present it as a percentage.	Percentage	World Development Indicators, World Bank.
PGDP	GDP per capita (current US\$)	GDP per capita is measured as the gross domestic product divided by the population at the midpoint of the year.	Percentage	World Development Indicators, World Bank.
MTR	Mortality rate, infant (per 1,000 live births)	Infant mortality rate is the number of infants dying before reaching one year of age, per 1,000 live births in a given year.		World Development Indicators, World Bank.
GCF	Gross capital formation (% of GDP)	Consists of outlays on additions to the fixed assets of the economy plus net changes in the level of inventories.	Percentage	World Development Indicators, World Bank.

Source: Author's Computation (2023)

Nevertheless, the absence of certain limitations in the dataset must be acknowledged. Specifically, missing data for certain countries or years might affect the consistency of trends over time. Additionally, the governance indicators used in this study are based on perception; this could introduce biases that may impact the interpretation of the findings. These potential data limitations were carefully considered during the evaluation process to minimize their effect on the results and conclusions.

3.3. Estimation Techniques

Principal Component Analysis (PCA)

According to Vyas & Kumaranayake (2006), Principal Component Analysis PCA is useful in situations when a study has two proxy variables that are highly correlated or provide similar information, it can reduce them to a single combined variable (principal component). Its primary goal is to simplify data

by keeping important details while using fewer variables (Premanand, 2023). This simplifies the analysis by working with a single variable instead of two. Moreover, if these two proxy variables capture different aspects of the same core idea, PCA can merge them into one, capturing what they have in common (Kolenikov & Angeles, 2009). This can provide a more comprehensive measure of the analysis. The benefits of principal component analysis (PCA) include simplifying analysis, reducing multicollinearity, and enhancing model performance. One important requirement for PCA is ensuring that the variables are correlated (Vyas & Kumaranayake, 2006).

System GMM estimation

The study adopted a dynamic panel regression model in estimating the relationship between governance indicators and SDG1 “No Poverty”. Two-step system GMM approach was adopted as the estimation technique for the dynamic model as it addresses cross-country variations, takes care of issues related to unobserved heterogeneity by considering time-invariant omitted variables, and employs internal instruments to handle concerns regarding reverse causality and endogeneity of the explanatory variables. Furthermore, the two-step system GMM approach boasts additional strengths compared to the difference GMM method originally proposed by Arellano and Bond (1991) (Gossel, 2022).

Post estimation Test

The study employs post-estimation tests, specifically the Sargan test for overidentifying restrictions and the Arellano-Bond test to check for second-order serial correlation in the error term, with the aim of verifying the reliability of the estimator. The Sargan test is a post-estimation test in econometrics, primarily used in instrumental variable (IV) estimation. It assesses the validity of instruments by evaluating over identifying restrictions in a model (Bastardoz et al., 2023). The test generates a chi-squared statistic, comparing it to critical values to determine instrument validity and model specification (Roodman, 2009). The Arellano-Bond test is an important tool in panel data analysis for detecting and addressing serial correlation in the error terms of econometric models. It helps ensure that the estimated results are reliable and that the model assumptions are met (Osborne & Waters, 2019).

4. Results

This section comprises Principal Component Analysis (PCA), descriptive statistics, pair wise correlation analysis results, Model estimation results and post-estimation results.

4.1 Principal Component Analysis (PCA)

Table 2 presents the result of the Principal Component Analysis (PCA), showing two components; Comp1 and Comp2 which cut across the three governance dimensions: political governance (Polgov), economic governance (Ecogov), and institutional governance (Instgov).

Table 2. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) Result

	Polgov	Ecogov	Instgov
Comp1	0.8191	0.9468	0.9453
Comp2	0.1809	0.0532	0.0547

Source: Author’s Computation (2023)

Comp1 captures the higher proportion of the combined variables, with 81.91%, 94.68%, and 94.53% for Polgov, Ecogov, and Instgov respectively. On the other hand, Comp2 retains a much smaller proportion of the variance, accounting for 18.09%, 5.32%, and 5.47% respectively. Based on the overwhelming explanatory power of Comp1 across all three categories, it was retained for the construction of the new governance indicators used in the analysis. This suggests that Comp1 sufficiently represents the underlying information in each category, justifying the application of PCA in simplifying the indicators for the study.

4.2 Descriptive Statistics

Table 3 presents the descriptive statistics of the study variables, comprising 315 observations across 45 countries for the period under review. SDG1.1.1 records a mean value of 28.88 with a standard deviation

of 22.39, a minimum value of 0.04 observed in Mauritius, and a maximum of 79.61 in Burundi. SDG1.4.1 has a mean of 73.24 and standard deviation of 18.50, with the Democratic Republic of Congo and Mauritius reporting the lowest and highest scores, respectively. SDG1.a.1 has a mean value of 1.15 and a standard deviation of 1.30, ranging from 0.0035 in Algeria to 8.09 in Burundi.

Table 3. Descriptive statistics of the variables

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
SDG111	315	28.87537	22.39309	.04	79.61
SDG141	315	73.23572	18.50183	15.14076	99.9958
SDG1a1	315	1.151658	1.301407	.00351	8.09188
VA	315	-.502442	.6783316	-1.851002	.9741873
RQ	315	-.6385921	.536897	-1.684896	1.190632
RL	315	-.6046906	.5665711	-1.841541	.9255343
CC	315	-.6029278	.5970513	-1.581135	1.035422
GE	315	-.7139336	.5826594	-1.791292	1.16092
PS	315	-.648575	.7865559	-2.352437	1.111055
Polgov	315	1.43e-08	1.27992	-2.90626	2.919032
Ecogov	315	-1.71e-08	1.376048	-2.458407	4.625754
Instgov	315	5.71e-09	1.374961	-2.645273	3.336533
CPI	315	256.8825	986.3825	0	16245.89
PGDP	315	2091.899	2132.495	216.8274	11643.46
POPG	315	2.344153	.7936158	.0022907	3.867091
MTR	315	44.28762	18.19634	11.7	95.5
GCF	315	23.13738	11.85847	0	79.40108

Source: Author's Computation (2023)

Voice and Accountability (VA) has an average of -0.50 with a standard deviation of 0.68. Regulatory Quality (RQ), Rule of Law (RL), and Control of Corruption (CC) have similar average values of around -0.60 and standard deviations ranging between 0.53 and 0.60. Government Effectiveness (GE) records an average of -0.71 and Political Stability (PS) -0.65, indicating general governance challenges across the region. For the composite governance indicators, Political Governance (Polgov), Economic Governance (Ecogov), and Institutional Governance (Instgov) all have means close to zero with standard deviations of approximately 1.28, 1.38, and 1.38 respectively, suggesting normalized scores post-principal component transformation. Among control variables, the Consumer Price Index (CPI) shows high variability, with a mean of 256.88 and a standard deviation of 986.38. GDP per capita averages around \$2,092, with Mauritius reaching over \$11,600, in stark contrast to Burundi's low of about \$217. Population Growth (POPG) and Mortality Rate (MTR) record mean values of 2.34 and 44.29, respectively. Gross Capital Formation (GCF) averages 23.14, reflecting moderate investment levels across the sample.

4.3 Pairwise Correlation Analysis

Tables 4a and 4b show the results of the Pairwise Correlation Analysis.

Table 4a. Pairwise Correlation Analysis

	SDG111	SDG141	SDG1a1	VA	RQ	RL	CC	GE
SDG111	1.0000							
SDG141	-0.5130	1.0000						
SDG1a1	0.6271	-0.2617	1.0000					
VA	-0.2797	0.3022	-0.1368	1.0000				
RQ	-0.4002	0.3332	-0.3121	0.6926	1.0000			
RL	-0.5182	0.4154	-0.3891	0.7051	0.8872	1.0000		
CC	-0.4570	0.3563	-0.2788	0.6933	0.8190	0.8905	1.0000	
GE	-0.5578	0.4394	-0.4568	0.6427	0.8935	0.9239	0.8554	1.0000

PS	-0.2959	0.3222	-0.2081	0.6382	0.6594	0.7035	0.6753	0.6437
Polgov	-0.3180	0.3449	-0.1905	0.9050	0.7469	0.7782	0.7561	0.7107
Ecogov	-0.4923	0.3970	-0.3951	0.6861	0.9730	0.9307	0.8604	0.9730
Instgov	-0.5016	0.3969	-0.3435	0.7192	0.8774	0.9722	0.9722	0.9151
CPI	-0.0137	0.0202	0.0043	-0.1389	-0.1656	-0.1134	-0.1281	-0.1482
PGDP	-0.6043	0.4434	-0.5223	0.3809	0.5966	0.5819	0.4696	0.6658
POPG	0.4710	-0.4595	0.2367	-0.3839	-0.4710	-0.5002	-0.5046	-0.5174
MTR	0.4991	-0.4323	0.4134	-0.2460	-0.4672	-0.6348	-0.4657	-0.6701
GCF	-0.0192	-0.0805	-0.1093	0.0634	-0.0074	0.0553	0.1340	0.1305

Source: Author's Computation (2023)

Table 4b. Pairwise Correlation Analysis result

	PS	Polgov	Ecogov	Instgov	CPI	PGDP	POPG	POPG	MTR
PS	1.0000								
Polgov	0.9050	1.0000							
Ecogov	0.6696	0.7490	1.0000						
Instgov	0.7091	0.7891	0.9211	1.0000					
CPI	-0.1345	-0.1511	-0.1614	-0.1244	1.0000				
PGDP	0.4926	0.4825	0.6487	0.5408	-0.0614	1.0000			
POPG	-0.4222	-0.4453	-0.5079	-0.5168	0.0365	-0.6271	1.0000		
MTR	-0.4447	-0.3815	-0.5844	-0.5659	-0.0293	-0.5529	0.4637	1.0000	
GCF	0.1097	0.0955	0.0629	0.0973	-0.1633	-0.0756	0.1506	-0.1155	1.0000

Source: Author's Computation (2023)

From Tables 4a and 4b, it can be inferred from the pairwise correlation result that, there exists a perfect or exact linear relationship among some of the independent variables i.e. high correlation values among variables such as Voice and Accountability, Regulatory Quality, Rule of Law, and the composite governance indicators (Polgov, Ecogov, Instgov) suggest significant multicollinearity. Therefore, these variables will not be included together in a single model; instead, each variable will be analyzed separately to address the challenge posed by the presence of a perfect linear relationship among them which ensures the reliability of the model estimations.

4.4 Model Estimation and Results

This section presents the econometric investigation to establish the relationship between governance and sustainable development in Africa. Two different estimation models were employed for the random panel model defined in Equation 3.2. The first model assesses how governance indicators have impacted SDG1, that is, "No Poverty" in Africa. The second model examines how the three governance categories derived from PCA influence SDG1 (SDG 1.1.1, SDG 1.4.1, and SDG 1.a.1) in Africa (Asongu & Odhiambo, 2021).

Table 5. Two step GMM estimation result (SDG1.1.1)

VARIABLES	SDG1.1.1					
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
L.SDG111	0.910*** (0.0237)	0.870*** (0.0214)	0.900*** (0.0230)	0.944*** (0.0227)	1.015*** (0.0189)	0.950*** (0.0209)
VA	- 4.085*** (0.880)					
RQ		-3.299*** (0.721)				
RL			-3.266*** (0.840)			

CC				1.181		
				(0.986)		
GE					4.169***	
					(0.803)	
PS						-1.084***
						(0.277)
CPI	-7.72e-05***	-5.74e-05	-0.000118	-0.000118	-0.000109	-0.000126
	(1.58e-05)	(6.74e-05)	(7.92e-05)	(8.29e-05)	(8.44e-05)	(8.57e-05)
PGDP	-0.000838***	-0.000773**	-0.000782**	-0.000681**	-0.000663**	-0.000778**
	(0.000310)	(0.000234)	(0.000232)	(0.000246)	(0.000250)	(0.000252)
POPG	-0.807*	-0.554*	-0.250	-0.362	-1.001**	-0.272
	(0.475)	(0.299)	(0.418)	(0.357)	(0.437)	(0.403)
MTR	-0.238***	-0.262***	-0.306***	-0.319***	-0.324***	-0.314***
	(0.0384)	(0.0362)	(0.0405)	(0.0395)	(0.0361)	(0.0397)
GCF	-0.0165	0.00908	0.00659	0.0172	-0.000914	0.0119
	(0.0150)	(0.0136)	(0.0123)	(0.0122)	(0.0152)	(0.0135)
Sargan	0.0539	0.1536	0.1600	0.0963	0.0591	0.0591
AR2	0.0747	0.1536	0.1285	0.1061	0.1585	0.0945
Constant	14.43***	14.61***	15.22***	16.69***	18.88***	15.12***
	(2.269)	(1.901)	(2.254)	(2.526)	(2.852)	(2.243)
Observations	270	270	270	270	270	270

Standard errors in parentheses: *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Source: Author's computation (2023)

Table 5 presents a two-step GMM estimation result on the influence of governance indicators on SDG 1.1.1 (Employed population below international poverty line, by sex and age (%)) across Africa. The results show that all governance indicators have significant impact on the employed population below the poverty line, except on Control of Corruption. The significant governance variables generally have an inverse relationship with SDG 1.1.1. This means that higher levels of governance indicators except for Government Effectiveness are associated with fewer people employed below the poverty line, based on sex and age. Interestingly, better Government Effectiveness seems to have the opposite effect, increasing the proportion of employed people above the poverty line. Inflation is significant in model 1, where it shows a negative impact on employment levels below the poverty line. Additionally, GDP per capita and Mortality Rate are consistently significant across all models, both showing an inverse relationship with SDG 1.1.1.

Drawing inference from the Sargan test of over identifying restrictions and the Arelleno-Bond test for zero autocorrelation in first differenced error result in the post estimation result of table 5, only model 2 and 3 results are valid given that the probability value is greater than 0.10 or 10%, thus specification and estimation for both models are valid.

Table 6. Two step GMM estimation results (SDG1.4.1)

VARIABLES	SDG1.4.1					
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
L.SDG141	-0.0199	-0.0291	-0.00199	-0.0203	-0.0342	-0.0259
	(0.0531)	(0.0536)	(0.0493)	(0.0516)	(0.0551)	(0.0596)
VA	9.646					

	(6.228)					
RQ		-3.260				
		(7.777)				
RL			7.398			
			(10.31)			
CC				5.759		
				(6.071)		
GE					15.46*	
					(8.549)	
PS						9.309***
						(3.192)
CPI	0.000319	0.000458	0.000313	0.000458	0.000672	0.000742
	(0.000680)	(0.000593)	(0.000565)	(0.000660)	(0.000808)	(0.000717)
PGDP	0.00355***	0.00279**	0.00263**	0.00329***	0.00384***	0.00405***
	(0.00125)	(0.00114)	(0.00119)	(0.00121)	(0.00127)	(0.00120)
POPG	0.908	-2.787	-1.789	-1.078	-0.324	-0.0419
	(2.792)	(2.529)	(2.494)	(2.668)	(2.791)	(3.169)
MTR	-0.405**	-0.297	-0.231	-0.199	-0.150	-0.248
	(0.199)	(0.197)	(0.189)	(0.182)	(0.210)	(0.184)
GCF	-0.170	-0.264	-0.225	-0.118	-0.158	-0.115
	(0.151)	(0.176)	(0.172)	(0.161)	(0.164)	(0.167)
Sargan	0.6709	0.4638	0.4834	0.4929	0.5326	0.6294
AR2	0.2688	0.2716	0.2296	0.2737	0.2680	0.2830
Constant	91.29***	94.34***	92.51***	85.47***	89.74***	85.44***
	(12.96)	(13.53)	(13.27)	(11.82)	(12.45)	(12.78)
Observations	270	270	270	270	270	270

Standard errors in parentheses: *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Source: Author's computation (2023)

Table 6 presents the two-step GMM estimation results based on the influence of governance indicators (VA, RQ, RL, CC, GE and PS) impacts on SDG 1.4.1 (Proportion of population using basic drinking water services, by location (%)) in Africa. From the result, all governance indicator variables have no significant impact on SDG1.4.1 except government effectiveness and political stability where both government effectiveness and political stability exerts significant and positive impact on SDG 1.4.1. This implies that, an increased in government effectiveness and improved political stability in a country tends to raise the proportion of population using basic drinking water services, by location (%). This result does not correlate with the study of Akpan & Effiong (2012). From the control variables, only GDP per capita shows a significant and positive relationship with SDG 1.4.1 which suggests that, higher level of GDP per capita tends to increase the proportion of population using basic drinking water services, by location. This collaborates with the study of Asongu & Odhiambo (2020).

The result of the Sargan test shows some restrictions on the Arelleno-Bond test for zero autocorrelation on first-differenced errors. The post-estimation results in Table 6 indicate that all models are deemed valid. This conclusion is drawn because the probability value exceeds 0.10, or 10%, indicating the validity of the model specifications and estimations for all models.

Table 7. Two step GMM estimation results (SDG1.a.1)

VARIABLES	SDG1.a.1					
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
L.SDG1a1	0.507***	0.603***	0.556***	0.535***	0.549***	0.520***
	(0.0339)	(0.0237)	(0.0247)	(0.0273)	(0.0232)	(0.0313)

VA	-0.434***					
	(0.111)					
RQ		0.0437				
		(0.108)				
RL			-0.381***			
			(0.111)			
CC				-0.575***		
				(0.117)		
GE					-0.583***	
					(0.158)	
PS						-0.372***
						(0.0690)
CPI	4.06e-05***	4.22e-05***	3.53e-05***	4.40e-05***	4.16e-05***	2.73e-05***
	(4.88e-06)	(6.09e-06)	(5.83e-06)	(5.26e-06)	(5.13e-06)	(4.89e-06)
PGDP	-0.000190** *	-0.000201** *	-0.000166* *	-0.000173** *	-0.000146* *	-0.000182** *
	(7.31e-05)	(6.71e-05)	(7.04e-05)	(6.52e-05)	(6.76e-05)	(6.74e-05)
POPG	-0.206***	0.157**	0.0881*	-0.107**	0.0264	-0.0521
	(0.0524)	(0.0737)	(0.0473)	(0.0536)	(0.0681)	(0.0495)
MTR	0.0269***	0.0139**	0.0163***	0.0204***	0.0215***	0.0208***
	(0.00485)	(0.00542)	(0.00571)	(0.00529)	(0.00615)	(0.00582)
GCF	-0.00630***	-0.00614***	-0.00706** *	-0.00405***	-0.00355**	-0.00521***
	(0.00144)	(0.00145)	(0.00147)	(0.00151)	(0.00167)	(0.00186)
Sargan	0.3077	0.1187	0.2182	0.2881	0.2961	0.2479
AR2	0.1723	0.1630	0.1882	0.1754	0.1737	0.1691
Constant	0.198	0.0189	-0.121	0.00714	-0.504*	0.0138
	(0.211)	(0.232)	(0.201)	(0.256)	(0.270)	(0.221)
Observations	270	270	270	270	270	270

Standard errors in parentheses: *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Source: Author's computation (2023)

Table 7 presents the two-step GMM estimation results on the influence of governance indicators (VA, RQ, RL, CC, GE, and PS) on SDG 1.a.1 (Official development assistance grants for poverty reduction, by recipient countries as a percentage of GNI) in Africa. The findings revealed that all governance indicator variables, except regulatory quality (RQ), has significant impact on SDG 1.a.1. Specifically, voice and accountability, rule of law, control of corruption, government effectiveness, and political stability (VA, RL, CC, GE, and PS) exert a negative and significant influence on official development assistance grants for poverty reduction. The significant governance indicators: Voice and Accountability, Rule of Law, Control of Corruption, Government Effectiveness, and Political Stability suggests that as African countries strengthen these aspects of governance, they become more self-reliant, reducing their dependence on foreign aid for poverty reduction. A robust legal system, lower corruption, and more effective governance allow for better resource allocation and sustainable development, thus decreasing the need for external assistance. This indicates that, higher level of these governance indicators reduces SDG 1.a.1 in Africa, which was in line with the work of Asongu & Odhiambo (2020). In contrast, Regulatory Quality didn't show any significant impact, possibly due to its indirect or less immediate effects on foreign aid for poverty alleviation in African countries.

As for control variables, they were all significant across all models. Infant mortality rate and inflation exhibit positive and significant relationships with SDG 1.a.1. This suggests that higher levels of infant mortality and inflation rate increase official development assistance grants for poverty reduction, by

recipient countries in Africa. Conversely, GDP per capita and gross capital formation have a negative and significant relationship with SDG 1.a.1, which indicate that higher GDP per capita and gross capital formation are associated with lower Official development assistance grants for poverty reduction in Africa. This finding is consistent with the work of Ahmed & Anifowose (2023).

Population growth also shows a positive and significant relationship with SDG 1.a.1 in most of the models, except for models 1, 4, and 6. This suggests that changes in population growth rates can either result in the rise or fall of official development assistance grants for poverty reduction, depending on the sign. The post-estimation results in Table 7 confirmed the results for all models are considered to be valid.

Table 8. Two step GMM estimation result (SDG 1.1.1 and SDG 1.4.1)

VARIABLES	SDG 1.1.1			SDG 1.4.1		
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
L.SDG111	0.935*** (0.0238)	0.966*** (0.0213)	0.917*** (0.0219)			
L.SDG141				-0.0645 (0.0506)	-0.0479 (0.0543)	-0.0506 (0.0528)
Polgov	-1.438*** (0.392)			4.520 (2.841)		
Ecogov		0.946** (0.408)			4.732 (3.475)	
Instgov			-0.503 (0.517)			0.734 (4.384)
CPI	-0.000108 (6.94e-05)	-0.000130 (0.000102)	-0.000108 (8.14e-05)	0.000653 (0.000876)	0.000725 (0.000886)	0.000423 (0.000650)
PGDP	-0.000761** * (0.000266)	-0.000637* * (0.000248)	-0.000744** * (0.000249)	0.00392** * (0.00119)	0.00426** * (0.00117)	0.00304** * (0.00116)
POPG	0.408 (0.575)	0.0217 (0.364)	0.0640 (0.460)	1.032 (2.842)	0.232 (2.658)	-1.471 (2.531)
MTR	-0.297*** (0.0401)	-0.328*** (0.0437)	-0.313*** (0.0429)	-0.178 (0.169)	-0.0707 (0.181)	-0.112 (0.194)
GCF	0.0138* (0.00728)	0.0122 (0.00854)	0.0113 (0.00778)	-0.149 (0.157)	-0.0674 (0.165)	-0.142 (0.176)
Sargan result	0.2425	0.1134	0.1775	0.6701	0.3735	0.4554
AR(2)	0.0848	0.1349	0.1221	0.4257	0.4212	0.4137
Constant	14.35*** (2.085)	14.71*** (2.486)	15.80*** (2.145)	78.62*** (10.23)	72.17*** (12.85)	82.94*** (14.38)
Observations	247	247	247	247	247	247

Standard errors in parentheses: *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Source: Author's computation (2023)

Table 8 presents the two-step GMM estimation results for SDG 1.1.1 (Employed population below the international poverty line, by sex and age) and SDG 1.4.1 (Proportion of the population using basic drinking water services, by location) across African countries, analyzing the impact of three governance categories: Political Governance (Polgov), Economic Governance (Ecogov), and Institutional Governance (Instgov).

The findings reveal that only Political and Economic Governance have significant impacts on SDG 1.1.1 in Africa. Specifically, Political Governance has a negative relationship with SDG 1.1.1,

suggesting that in countries with weaker political systems and inefficient governance processes, a higher proportion of the population falls below the poverty line. In contrast, Economic Governance shows a positive relationship with SDG 1.1.1, indicating that in countries with better economic governance, which boosts the government's ability to design and implement policies, there is a reduction in poverty, reflected in higher employment rates above the poverty line. This result is in line with the study found in Asongu & Odhiambo (2021). However, none of the governance categories; Political, Economic, or Institutional—showed a significant impact on SDG 1.4.1, which measures the proportion of the population with access to basic drinking water services, in African countries. This suggests that while governance influences poverty and employment, it does not seem to directly affect access to basic services such as drinking water in the region.

Among all the control variables, GDP per capita shows a negative and significant relationship with SDG 1.1.1, indicating that higher GDP per capita is linked to a lower proportion of the employed population below the international poverty line in African countries. Conversely, GDP per capita has a positive and significant relationship with SDG 1.4.1, suggesting that as GDP per capita increases, the proportion of the population with access to basic drinking water services also improves. Infant mortality rate has a significant and inverse relationship with SDG 1.1.1; higher mortality rates are associated with a reduction in the employed population above the poverty line. However, infant mortality has no significant impact on SDG 1.4.1, highlighting its limited influence on access to basic drinking water.

The post-estimation results, shown in Table 8, indicate that all models, except for Model 1, are valid. This conclusion is drawn based on the probability value exceeding 0.10, which confirms the validity of the model specifications and estimations for all models excluding Model 1.

Table 9. Two step GMM estimation result (impact of three governance categories on SDG 1.a.1)

VARIABLES	SDG 1.a.1		
	(1)	(2)	(3)
L.SDG1a1	0.357*** (0.0166)	0.454*** (0.0267)	0.345*** (0.0368)
Polgov	-0.425*** (0.0562)		
Ecogov		-0.346*** (0.107)	
Instgov			-0.586*** (0.104)
CPI	3.36e-05*** (3.12e-06)	4.97e-05*** (3.76e-06)	4.33e-05*** (2.65e-06)
PGDP	-0.000185*** (5.89e-05)	-0.000162*** (5.54e-05)	-0.000213*** (4.65e-05)
POPG	-0.000318 (0.0533)	0.0780 (0.0734)	-0.0764 (0.0633)
MTR	0.0186*** (0.00602)	0.0159*** (0.00500)	0.0110* (0.00609)
GCF	-0.00710*** (0.00159)	-0.00558** (0.00277)	-0.00605*** (0.00197)
Sargan result	0.2700	0.3148	0.1506
AR(2)	0.2345	0.2521	0.3148
Constant	0.448 (0.286)	0.328 (0.239)	1.059*** (0.270)
Observations	247	247	247

Standard errors in parentheses: *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Source: Author's computation (2023)

Table 9 presents the two-step GMM estimation results on the impact of three governance categories: political, economic, and institutional governance on SDG 1.a.1 (Official development assistance grants for poverty reduction, by recipient countries as a percentage of GNI) in Africa. The results show that all three governance categories have a negative and significant impact on SDG 1.a.1. Specifically, improvements in political governance, economic governance, and institutional governance are associated with a decrease in the level of official development assistance grants for poverty reduction in Africa. This suggests that as the ease of selecting and replacing those in authority (political governance) improves, government policy effectiveness (economic governance) strengthens, and respect for citizens and institutions increases (institutional governance), the need for official development assistance (ODA) for poverty reduction falls. This aligns with the findings of Asongu & Odhiambo (2021).

Among the control variables, population growth does not significantly affect SDG 1.a.1, while inflation rate and infant mortality rate show a positive and significant relationship with Official Development Assistance for poverty reduction, implying that higher levels of inflation and infant mortality lead to increased Official Development Assistance grants. Both GDP per capita and gross capital formation have a negative and significant relationship with SDG 1.a.1, indicating that as these variables increase, the need for Official Development Assistance grants for poverty reduction decreases. Population growth, while generally insignificant, shows a mixed relationship, exerting a negative impact on most models but a positive relationship in Model 2, reflecting that population growth can either increase or decrease Official Development Assistance for poverty reduction depending on the model. The post-estimation results presented in Table 9 show that all models are statistically significant. These findings confirm the reliability of all models.

5. Conclusions and Recommendations

This study investigated the vital role of governance in achieving SDG1 "No Poverty" across African countries which fills a noticeable gap in existing literature by examining the specific influence of political, economic, and institutional governance on sub indicators of SDG1. Using panel data from 45 African countries between 2015 and 2021, the study adopted the two-step system GMM technique to assess the relationship between governance and multiple SDG1 sub-indicators. The results reaffirm that governance plays a significant role not just as a background factor but a direct and significant influence on poverty reduction efforts.

Based on validity of models, Rule of Law and Regulatory Quality were found to significantly reduce the proportion of employed individuals living below the international poverty line (SDG 1.1.1), highlighting the role of strong legal institutions and fair regulatory systems in protecting the vulnerable in society. Government Effectiveness and Political Stability positively influenced SDG 1.4.1 by improving access to basic services like clean drinking water, especially in areas lacking them. Regarding official development assistance for poverty reduction (SDG 1.a.1), several governance indicators including Voice and Accountability, Rule of Law, Control of Corruption, Government Effectiveness, and Political Stability were all significant and exhibited a negative relationship. This implies that as governance improves, African countries are inclined to reduce their reliance on foreign aid and build stronger internal systems for tackling poverty.

Economic governance (ecogov) highlights a positive and significant influence on the same sub-indicator, indicating that a government's capacity to formulate sound policies and deliver services can significantly reduce extreme poverty in African countries. However, institutional governance was found to have no significant impact on this indicator. In relation to SDG 1.a.1 which captures official development assistance (ODA) for poverty reduction, all three governance indicators; political, economic, and Institutional exhibits a significant and negative relationship. This finding indicates that as governance structures improve across African countries, the reliance on external development aid for poverty reduction diminishes suggesting that better governance can help African countries strengthen internal mechanisms for addressing poverty, thereby reducing the need for foreign assistance. These results collectively point to governance reform as a strategic tool in the fight against poverty in Africa.

Based on these findings, it can be inferred that Economic governance showed significant relationship suggesting the need for governments to improve the effectiveness of their policy formulation and service delivery in ways that specifically target the vulnerable in the society rather than catering to interests of the elites. Although institutional governance showed no significant relationship to the employed population below the poverty line, its impact on the need for official development assistance suggests its importance in reducing aid dependency. Thus, building institutions that respect citizens' rights, enforce rules fairly, and facilitate meaningful civic engagement will be essential in tackling this issue.

Control variables also play a vital role in determining poverty outcomes. GDP per capita depicts a significant and negative relationship with SDG 1.1.1 while having a positive one with SDG 1.4.1, indicating that economic growth helps reduce extreme poverty and expand access to basic services like drinking water. Infant mortality rate had a significant and negative relationship with SDG 1.1.1, indicating that high mortality rates tend to suppress employment among the poor, though it showed no effect on access to water services. Additionally, variables like gross capital formation and mortality rate were significant in explaining official development assistance flows thereby confirming their relevance towards poverty reduction.

In conclusion, this study highlights the requirement of more than just economic growth or international aid in achieving SDG1 in Africa, it demands deliberate actions of governance. Government agencies must prioritize factors such as political stability, government effectiveness, and anti-corruption efforts, rule of law enforcement, regulatory quality, and citizen engagement while being accountable for their actions. Policies should be targeted towards the most vulnerable populations to reduce poverty rates in the region. In relation to the three dimensions of government, economic governance was found to have a significant influence on employed population living below the international poverty line, while all three governance dimensions significantly influence the levels of official development assistance on poverty reduction. These findings make a compelling case for African governments to treat governance not as a secondary concern, but as a key approach in the overall effort to eradicate poverty across the continent. These efforts will enhance effective governance contribution towards SDG1 "No Poverty," thereby ensuring sound government operations, fostering economic growth and development.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

References

1. African Development Bank. (2023). *Tracking Africa's progress in figures: Governance, fragility, and security*. <https://www.afdb.org/en/knowledge/publications/tracking-africa%E2%80%99s-progress-in-figures/governance-fragility-and-security>
2. Ahmed, A., & Anifowose, M. (2023). Corruption, corporate governance, and sustainable development goals in Africa. *Corporate Governance*, 24(3). <https://doi.org/10.1108/CG-07-2022-0311>
3. Akpan, G. E., & Effiong, E. L. (2012). Governance and development performance: a cross-country analysis of Sub-Saharan Africa. *Governance*, 3(14), 54-67.
4. Allen, C., Breuer, A., Kercher, J., Leininger, J., & Balasubramanian, P. (2022). *Connections that matter: How the Quality of Governance Institutions May Be the Booster Shot We Need to Reduce Poverty and Inequality: A systematic literature review on SDG 16 Interlinkages with SDG 1 and SDG 10*. United Nations Development Program (UNDP). https://www.undp.org/sites/g/files/zskgke326/files/2022-07/UNDP%20Oslo%2C%20policy%20option%201%20Report%2C%20FINAL_WEB.pdf

5. Arellano, M & Bond, S (1991). Some tests of specification for panel data: Monte Carlo evidence and application to employment equations. *The Review of Economic Studies*, 58(2), 277-297.
6. Asongu, S. A., & Odhiambo, N. M. (2020). Income levels, governance and inclusive human development in Sub-Saharan Africa. *Applied Research in Quality of Life*, 16, 71-103.
7. Asongu, S. A., & Odhiambo, N. M. (2021). Enhancing governance for environmental sustainability in Sub-Saharan Africa. *Energy Exploration & Exploitation*, 39(1), 444-463.
8. Ayodeji, I. O., & Abdulganiyu, T. A. (2022). Poverty, Governance and Economic Progression: Evidence from Nigeria. *African Development Finance Journal*, 3(2), 60-77.
9. Bağ, I. (2024). *Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs): Concept and measurement. In the role of financial markets in achieving the sustainable development goals*. Edward Elgar Publishing, 15-41. <https://doi.org/10.4337/9781035323265.00009>
10. Balasubramanian, P., Breuer, A., Leininger, J., Cameron, A., & Kercher, J. (2022). *Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) 16: A governance compass towards just transition?* (No. 4/2022). IDOS Policy Brief.
11. Barbier, E. B., & Burgess, J. C. (2021). Institutional quality, governance and progress towards the SDGs. *Sustainability*, 13(21), 11798.
12. Bastardo, N., Matthews, M. J., Sajons, G. B., Ransom, T., Kelemen, T. K., & Matthews, S. H. (2023). Instrumental variables estimation: Assumptions, pitfalls, and guidelines. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 34(1), 101673.
13. Dankumo, A. M., Ishak, S., Bani, Y., & Hamza, H. Z. (2021). Governance, public expenditure, trade and poverty reduction in sub-Saharan African countries. *Journal Ekonomi dan Studi Pembangunan*, 13(1), 16-35.
14. DevelopmentAid. (2023). *Poverty rates in Africa: A global perspective*. <https://www.developmentaid.org/news-stream/post/84943/highest-poverty-rates-in-africa>
15. Forestier, O., & Kim, R. E. (2020). Cherry-picking the Sustainable Development Goals: Goal prioritization by national governments and implications for global governance. *Sustainable Development*, 28(5), 1269-1278
16. Gossel, S. (2022). FDI and inequality in Sub-Saharan Africa: Does democracy matter?. *International Journal of Emerging Markets*, 19(1), 33-55. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJOEM-03-2021-0321>
17. Haldar, A., Sethi, N., Jena, P. K., & Padhan, P. C. (2023). Towards achieving Sustainable Development Goal 7 in sub-Saharan Africa: Role of governance and renewable energy. *Sustainable Development*, 31(4), 2446-2463. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sd.2521>
18. Kerandi, A. M. (2008). Governance Agenda for Sub-Saharan Africa: Issues and Challenges. *Federal Governance*, 5(1), 1-22.
19. Kolenikov, S., & Angeles, G. (2009). Socioeconomic status measurement with discrete proxy variables: Is principal component analysis a reliable answer?. *Review of Income and Wealth*, 55(1), 128-165.
20. Kwon, H. J., & Kim, E. (2014). Poverty reduction and good governance: Examining the rationale of the Millennium Development Goals. *Development and Change*, 45(2), 353-375.
21. Leke, O., & Monisola, J. (2015). Governance and poverty reduction in Nigeria. *Governance*, 5(4).
22. Ogunniyi, A. I., Mavrotas, G., Olagunju, K. O., Fadare, O., & Adedoyin, R. (2020). Governance quality, remittances and their implications for food and nutrition security in Sub-Saharan Africa. *World Development*, 127, 104752.
23. Osborne, J. W. & Waters, E. (2019). Four assumptions of multiple regressions that researchers should always test. *Practical Assessment, Research, and Evaluation*, 8(1), 2.

24. Premanand, S. (2023). *An introductory note on Principal Component Analysis*. Analytics Vidhya. [https://www.analyticsvidhya.com/blog/2022/07/principal-component-analysis-beginner-friendly/#:~:text=Principal%20Component%20Analysis%20\(PCA\)&text=Reducing%20the%20number%20of%20variables,Correlated%20features%20to%20Independent%20features](https://www.analyticsvidhya.com/blog/2022/07/principal-component-analysis-beginner-friendly/#:~:text=Principal%20Component%20Analysis%20(PCA)&text=Reducing%20the%20number%20of%20variables,Correlated%20features%20to%20Independent%20features)
25. Reuters. (2024). *African progress backslides: Coups, war persist*. <https://www.reuters.com/world/africa/african-progress-backslides-coups-war-persist-2024-10-2>
26. Roodman, D. (2009). A note on the theme of too many instruments. *Oxford Bulletin of Economics and Statistics*, 71(1), 135-158.
27. Sadiq, M., Ngo, T. Q., Pantamee, A. A., Khudoykulov, K., Ngan, T. T., & Tan, L. P. (2023). The role of environmental social and governance in achieving sustainable development goals: evidence from ASEAN countries. *Economic Research-Ekonomska Istraživanja*, 36(1), 170-190.
28. Sustainable Development Report (2023). *Rankings: the overall performance of all 193 UN member states*. <https://dashboards.sdgindex.org/rankings>
29. The Global Goals (2023). *Goal 1: No Poverty*. https://www.globalgoals.org/goals/1-no-poverty/?gclid=CjwKCAjwv8qkBhAnEiwAkY-ahqDRkqX1Vs-VVaKIFrw3HeyuBtz6N6Xb5Wg26fi91tGISkUjcsfEjxoC-u8QAvD_BwE
30. Vaidya, H., & Chatterji, T. (2020). *SDG 11 Sustainable Cities and Communities*. In: Franco, I., Chatterji, T., Derbyshire, E., Tracey, J. (eds) *Actioning the Global Goals for Local Impact*. Science for Sustainable Societies. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-32-9927-6_12
31. Vyas-Doorgapersad, S. (2021). Global governance reforms to achieve Sustainable Development Goal One (no poverty) in BRICS. *Africa's Public Service Delivery & Performance Review*, 9(1), 9.
32. Vyas, S., & Kumaranayake, L. (2006). Constructing socio-economic status indices: How to use Principal Components Analysis. *Health policy and planning*, 21(6), 459-468.
33. World Bank (n.y.). *World Governance Indicators: Online*. Washington, DC. Retrieved from <http://data.worldbank.org/data-catalog/world-governance-indicators>.
34. WorldMetrics. (2023). *Africa poverty statistics: An overview*. <https://worldmetrics.org/africa-poverty-statistics>

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